

Using the Weighted Clause Ratio to Measure the Accuracy of Students' Responses to Epistemic Questions

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استخدام نسبة الجملة الموزونة في قياس الدقة اللغوية لإجابات الطلبة على الأسئلة المعرفية

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Abstract: This research aims to gauge the accuracy of students' verbal responses to epistemic questions in Algerian EFL classrooms. The purpose is to reach an estimation of the average accuracy level of students and to find out whether the scores of accuracy can be affected by the functional nature of teachers' questions. The implemented proxy measure of accuracy can assist language learners in self-reflecting on their oral performance and tracking their development, which can tremendously contribute to their self-efficacy. Essentially, the study represents an empirical research that adopts an ex-post facto design. It implements the weighted clause ratio (WCR) in measuring the accuracy of students' production. The findings are based on the analysis of 314 clauses produced after epistemic questions. The major results of this research showed that the mean score of accuracy related to epistemic questions was equal to a value of 0.92 (Av. Score= 0.92) which attests to the high accuracy level that was embedded in students' responses. The statistical difference between the mean accuracy scores corresponding to display (Av. Score= 0.93) and referential questions (Av. Score= 0.91) was insignificant (P-value= .29) which suggests that the accuracy of responses was not substantially affected by the functional nature of epistemic questions. Likewise, the obtained effect size implies that there is only a negligible difference (Cohen's d=-.126) between the accuracy scores of referential and display questions. More studies are still needed to confirm the obtained findings.

Keywords: accuracy; epistemic questions; weighted clause ratio; display questions; referential questions.

ملخص: يهدف هذا البحث إلى قياس الدقة اللغوية لإجابات الطلبة على الأسئلة المعرفية في الفصول الدراسية الجزائرية لتعليم اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية. الغرض من هذه الدراسة هو تقدير متوسط مستوى الدقة اللغوية لدى الطلبة ومعرفة ما إذا كانت درجات الدقة يمكن أن تتأثر بالطبيعة الوظيفية لأسئلة الأساتذة. إضافة إلى كون مقياس الدقة المستخدم أداة هامة للباحثين، يمكن أن يساعد أيضا متعلمي اللغة في تأمل وفحص أدائهم اللغوي وتتبع تطورهم الدراسي مما يؤدي إلى تعزيز كفاءتهم الذاتية. تمثل الدراسة بحثًا تجريبيًا يعتمد على تصميم باحثي رجعي (ex-post facto design). تم استعمال مقياس نسبة الجملة الموزونة (WCR) في تقدير دقة إنتاج الطلبة. تستند النتائج على تحليل 314 جملة تم إنتاجها ردا على الأسئلة المعرفية. أظهرت النتائج الرئيسية لهذا البحث أن درجة الدقة اللغوية المرتبطة بالأسئلة المعرفية كانت مساوية لقيمة متوسطة تعادل 0.92 (Av. Score = 0.92) مما أشار إلى وجود دقة لغوية عالية في المخرجات اللغوية للطلبة. كان الاختلاف الإحصائي بين متوسط درجات الدقة المتعلقة بالأسئلة التقييمية والأسئلة المرجعية ذو دلالة غير معنوية (P-value = .29) مما يشير إلى أن الطبيعة الوظيفية للأسئلة المعرفية لم يكن لها تأثير جوهري على المخرجات اللغوية للطلبة. وبالمثل، أشار حجم التأثير الذي تم الحصول عليه إلى وجود اختلاف ضئيل فقط (Cohen's d=-.126) بين درجات الدقة اللغوية المنتجة ردا على الأسئلة المرجعية والتقييمية. لا تزال هناك حاجة لمزيد من الدراسات لتأكيد النتائج التي تم الحصول عليها.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الدقة اللغوية؛ الأسئلة المعرفية؛ نسبة الجملة الموزونة؛ الأسئلة التقييمية؛ الأسئلة المرجعية.

I- Introduction

Language teachers play a prominent role in promoting the process of learners' acquisition since the various teaching techniques that teachers employ inside the classroom may shape the course of learners' development. The pace with which learners progress can also be partially dependent on the quality of input to which they are exposed during EFL courses (e. g. Krashen, 1982, 1985). Despite that the role of teachers is to lead and guide the learners toward attaining proficiency, it is quite intuitive that teaching practices are not always conducive to facilitative factors that accelerate the process of language acquisition. Some teaching behaviours like dominating the classroom talk can even impede the process of learning (Brown, 2001). The drawback of teachers' dominance of classroom talk is associated with the lesser time that would be available for students to practice and perform verbally in the target language (see Allwright, 1984). The critical role of language output, as a fundamental variable in attaining proficiency (Swain, 1985; 1995), would rise to the surface in similar teaching scenarios and oral deficiency might be consequently sensed in learners' performance because of lacking opportunities to communicate through the target system. One of the techniques that can be employed to minimise teachers' talk and conversely maximise the learners' production is to increase the frequency of questioning episodes inside EFL classrooms (Wright, 2016). The nature and quality of responses may help teachers in diagnosing the problems and difficulties experienced by students during oral performances. These problems can be assessed from three different angles: fluency, complexity, and accuracy; the three former dimensions are believed to be predictors of language proficiency (Housen & Kuiken, 2009; Housen, Kuiken & Vedder, 2012) .

The focus of this study is directed toward the third dimension represented in the accuracy of learners' oral production. The utilised proxy measure of accuracy, the weighted clause ratio, can act as an important resource for language researchers and educators who are interested in examining the properties of language output (see Foster and Wigglesworth, 2016). Also, language learners can benefit from the model by employing it to assess the accuracy of their performance in the target language which they want to have a command over. In this regard, Bandura (1986) explained that learners are endowed with many capacities that contribute to their level of self-efficacy and that self-reflection is the most important one since it enables the learners to assist and self-evaluate their behaviour. Obviously, the performance of learners in EFL is a verbal behaviour that can be assessed in terms of accuracy, considering that it is a factor that can predict language proficiency. Moreover, Bandura (1997) argued that "mastery experience" is one of the variables that can influence the development of self-efficacy beliefs since individuals who had prior experiences of successful performances tend to have a higher level of self-efficacy. Therefore, encouraging learners to self-reflect on their accuracy in language production and to evaluate their performance from time to time can give them a sense of success or a "mastery experience" as they would be able to track their developmental process throughout the course of EFL learning .

Particularly, this research aims to explore the accuracy of the language output produced by learners following display and referential questions (epistemic questions). Such a research

endeavour will help in assessing the accuracy of students' spontaneous production in EFL. The implemented instruments and procedures serve as a framework that language learners can replicate to self-reflect on the level of their accuracy during oral performances. Another objective is embodied in unravelling whether there is a correlation between the functional nature of epistemic questions and the level of accuracy manifested in students' responses. The obtained results will broaden our understanding of the actual accuracy level of students' spontaneous production since most of the examined responses in the database were supplied by students immediately after being exposed to questions. It should be noted that immediate answers are hereby considered to have a response wait-time which is equal to or less than one second .

To our best knowledge, this study represents the first research endeavour in the Algerian context of EFL education to examine the oral accuracy of students' output based on an empirical method that draws on classroom observational protocols, transcriptions, analytic schemes, and the statistical analysis of data. Likewise, there is a research gap in the literature regarding the impact of epistemic questions on the accuracy of language learners' production. Drawing on the earlier considerations, this study seeks to answer the following questions :

1-What is the mean accuracy level of students' responses to epistemic questions?

2-Which category of questioning techniques can lead to higher accuracy scores in EFL oral production?

The following null/alternative hypotheses are postulated :

- H_0 (null): There is no significant difference between the mean accuracy scores elicited by display/referential questions .

- H_1 (alternative): There is a significant difference between the mean accuracy scores elicited by display/referential questions .

Questioning techniques

Due to the content-oriented nature of the Algerian language curricula, most of the questions are expected to belong to the epistemic type of interrogatives (e. g. Gouider & Ameziane, 2022). This type of questions encompasses two main categories: display and referential interrogatives (Long & Sato, 1983). The former category refers to the questions that teachers ask with the purpose of evaluating the learners' knowledge about a given subject related to the content of classroom discussion (Kearsley, 1976). On the other hand, referential questions are asked with the genuine intention of seeking unknown information which cannot be anticipated beforehand (Long & Sato, 1983). The key difference between the two functional categories lies in the knowledge status of teachers at the instant in which questions are asked; that is whether the sought information is known or unknown beforehand. The context of discourse and the feedback move to be performed by teachers can help the analyst in determining the functional nature of epistemic questions by estimating whether the teacher intended to evaluate knowledge or to solicit new information from learners (Dalton-Puffer, 2007) .

Accuracy, Self-Efficacy and Language Proficiency

There is wide agreement among scholars about the impact of teachers' oral behaviour on learners' progress (Long, 1983). In this context, questions represent one of the key features that characterise teachers' talk (Brown, 2001; Tsui, 1995). The eliciting force of questions is what generally drives learners to produce in the target language given the fact that the imbalanced power relationships, entrenched in pedagogical discourse, can sometimes restrain students from freely taking the floor during classroom interaction (Burton, 1981; Wood, 1998). The consequent output to be produced by students can help language researchers in determining their actual level of accuracy and therefore have a better understanding of such a dimension which is directly correlated with language proficiency .

Before moving further in the presentation and the discussion of results, it is quite imperative to define the constructs of self-efficacy and accuracy. Bandura (1997) considers self-efficacy to be representative of the "beliefs in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments" (p. 3). Those beliefs in one's competence can be consolidated by the "mastery experience" (Bandura, 1997) and "the self-reflective capability" (Bandura, 1986) that learners are required to possess to achieve self-efficacy. Self-reflective capability can be exploited to assess the accuracy of one's output in the target language which would consequently lead to a mastery experience if progress in generating more accurate language forms is sensed by learners during their self-assessment. As far as accuracy is concerned, Housen and Kuiken (2009) define it as "the ability to produce error-free speech" (p. 461). The weighted clause ratio (WCR) is a scale of accuracy that can arguably act as a self-reflection asset for learners, and in turn, it can consequently develop their self-efficacy .

The present researcher has already examined the output produced by some of the participants involved in this study by probing the impact of epistemic questions on the length (Gouider & Ameziane, 2022) and the syntactic complexity of oral production (Gouider, 2022). The findings showed that the nature of functional questions had a significant influence on the length of output and the syntactic variants rooted in students' production. Referential questions tended to have a higher potential in eliciting lengthier and more complex responses. For the sake of unravelling whether a similar effect can be observed on the correctness of language output, the accuracy of those responses will be measured in this research .

Methodology

Research instruments and procedures

This research aims to fill the research gap regarding the effects of questioning techniques on the accuracy of students' production. To this end, the classroom interaction of six EFL lessons from two Algerian universities was recorded and then transcribed to promote the categorisation procedure. Long and Sato's (1983) dichotomy of epistemic questions was used for coding questions and the Weighted clause ratio was adopted in determining the accuracy scores of utterances. Epistemic questioning episodes were considered to be taken place whenever the

teacher issued a display or a referential question and were deemed to be over whenever the teacher made a feedback or a follow-up move subsequent to students' responses. In other words, all the answers that were immediately generated by students following an epistemic question were accounted for in the coding procedure as long as the teacher did not verbally intervene. The weighted clause ratio (WCR) was adopted for the classification of clausal accuracy. The framework was incorporated by assigning each produced clause with an accuracy score. A total of 314 clauses were examined in this study. The classification of clauses was dependent on the correctness of the generated utterances, which can range from entirely accurate clauses to those containing a third-level error that impedes communication. The allotted level of accuracy in WCR is contingent on the communicative adequacy associated with the generated clauses (Evans et al. 2014). The following table illustrates the used scale of accuracy :

Clause category	Definition	Accuracy Score
Entirely accurate	The clause is accurately constructed .	1
Level 1 error	The clause is embedded with minor errors that do not compromise meaning .	0.8
Level 2 error	The clause contains serious errors (e. g., verb tense, word choice, or word order), but still the meaning is recoverable, though not always obvious .	0.5
Level 3 error	The clause is embedded with very serious errors that make the intended meaning far from obvious and only partly recoverable .	0.1

Note. Adapted from Foster and Wigglesworth (2016)

It is important to note that only clauses were accounted for in this study, as elliptical and non-sentential utterances were excluded from the analysis .

Research findings

To begin with, the results were derived from the analysis of 315 clauses produced after the umbrella epistemic type of questions which is comprised of two main categories: display and referential questions. To answer the first research question "What is the mean accuracy level displayed in students' responses to epistemic questions?", the overall accuracy score pertaining to the clauses that followed epistemic questions was calculated. The findings revealed that the mean accuracy score manifested in students' responses to epistemic questions is equal to a value of 0.92. The average proportion of error-free clauses embodied 75.87% of the whole number of clauses generated by EFL students (see Table 2 below) .

Concerning the second research question "Which category of questioning techniques can lead to higher accuracy scores in EFL oral production?", the mean accuracy score of the clauses

elicited by referential questions was compared to that of display questions. The results showed that the average accuracy score of display questions (Av. Score= 0. 93; SD= 0. 15) was slightly higher than the one of referential questions (Av. Score= 0. 91; SD= 0. 17). Error-free clauses produced after the epistemic sub-categories represented proportions of 73. 08% and 77. 25%, corresponding to referential and display questions respectively. The next two tables demonstrate the results in more detail :

Table (2): Statistical dataset			
Variables	Ref. Qs	Disp. QS	Epistemic QS
Clauses	104	211	315
Accurate clauses	76	163	239
Clauses with level 1 errors	14	28	42
Clauses with level 2 errors	14	20	34
Clauses with level 3 errors	0	0	0
Weighting accurate clauses x 1	76	163	239
Level 1 x 0. 8	11. 2	22. 4	33. 6
Level 2 x 0. 5	7	10	17
Level 3 x 0. 1	0	0	0
Raw Total Score	94. 2	195. 4	289. 6
Weighted clause ratio (Raw total divided by total clauses)	0. 91	0. 93	0. 92
% Error-free clauses	73. 08%	77. 25%	75. 87%

Table (3): Descriptive Statistics related to the accuracy of responses following Epistemic question					
Dependent Variable	Epistemic Questions	N of Clauses	Mean Accuracy Score	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Accuracy scores	Referential	104	.9058	.17450	.01711
	Display	211	.9261	.15379	.01059

The earlier results imply the presence of a high accuracy level in students' responses to epistemic questions. The proportion of error-free clauses in students' production suggests that

only a quarter of the generated clauses had problematic features related to accuracy. The numerical difference that was reported between the mean accuracy scores of epistemic sub-categories may indicate that responses to display questions were slightly more accurate than their referential counterparts .

For the sake of testing the plausibility of the hypotheses, an independent samples t-test was employed. Since the assumption of the equality of variances was not violated ($p > .05$) as shown by Levene's test [$F= 4.48, p=.06$], the researcher proceeded by adopting results from the classical student t-test. The results indicated the presence of an insignificant difference ($p > .05$) between the accuracy scores corresponding to referential and display questions [$t(313) = -1.05, p=.29, 95\% CI= -.06, .02$]. Detailed statistics from the independent samples t-test are shown in table 4:

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	T	Df.	Significance		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						One-Sided p	Two-Sided p			Lower	Upper
Accuracy	Equal variances assumed	3.56	.06	-1.05	313.00	.15	.29*	-.02	.02	-.06	.02
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.01	183.75	.16	.31	-.02	.02	-.06	.02

*p-value $> .05$

Since no significant statistical difference is found, the alternative hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is embraced. The obtained Cohen's d effect size also attests to the negligible difference that existed between the accuracy scores corresponding to the two questioning categories [$d= -.126; 95\% CI= -.036, .109$]. The earlier results are provided hand in hand with complementary measurements of effect size in Table 5 :

	Standardizer ^a	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper

Accuracy scores	Cohen's d	.16090	-. 126	-. 361	.109
	Hedges' correction	.16129	-. 126	-. 360	.109
	Glass's delta	.15379	-. 132	-. 367	.103

a. The denominator used in estimating the effect sizes .
Cohen's d uses the pooled standard deviation .
Hedges' correction uses the pooled standard deviation, plus a correction factor .
Glass's delta uses the sample standard deviation of the control group .

Conclusion

This study involves an empirical endeavour that draws on classroom observation, transcriptions, analytical schemes and statistical analysis to gauge the level of clausal accuracy embedded in students' responses to epistemic questions. The findings showed that students' generic responses to epistemic questions were highly accurate (Av. Accuracy Score= 0. 92) since most of the generated clauses (75. 87%) were devoid of errors and no clauses with level 3 errors were reported. This implies that the output generated by students reflects a high level of EFL proficiency in terms of oral correctness (see Foster & Wigglesworth, 2016). The slightly high accuracy score and percentage of error-free clauses related to display questions (77. 25%), compared to the referential category (73. 08%), initially implied that display interrogatives may lead to more accurate responses. Likewise, the results initially entailed that referential questions could be more challenging in terms of accuracy, which would consequently lead to more corrective feedback and negative evidence from teachers than is the case for the display category .

Nevertheless, the student t-test showed that the numerical differences that existed between the two epistemic categories did not surpass the threshold of statistical significance ($p > . 05$). Similarly, the effect size indicated that there is only a negligible difference (Cohen's $d = -. 126$) between the obtained accuracy scores related to display and referential questions. The findings suggest that unlike the case of syntactic complexity (e. g. Brock, 1986; Gouider, 2022; Gouider & Ameziane, 2023) and the length of production (e. g. Gouider & Ameziane, 2022; Long & Sato, 1983), accuracy as a language learning factor is not significantly affected by the functional nature of epistemic questions. Still, the slight numerical difference reflected in the mean scores of accuracy should not be overlooked or entirely dismissed. There is a crucial need to conduct similar studies with the same instruments, or through other research tools and protocols, to reach more conclusive findings about the impact of epistemic questioning strategies on the accuracy of learners' production. Similar measures can be also used to track the changes that might occur in the scores of clausal accuracy when examining the output of learners at lower or higher proficiency levels. Such an endeavour can broaden our understanding of the trajectory that learners go through in their quest of attaining language proficiency. Likewise, language learners can implement WCR to assess and self-evaluate their accuracy and to trace their development, which may increase their motivation and sense of success. The mastery experience that language

learners would eventually go through can result in boosting their self-efficacy beliefs in relation to EFL learning .

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